

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

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Abstract

The UCDP Georeferenced Event Dataset (GED) is a spatially and temporally disaggregated dataset on fatal events from three types of organized violence (state-based conflict, non-state conflict, and one-sided violence) that occurred between 1 January 1989 and 31 December 2024. It is released annually by the Uppsala Conflict Data Program (UCDP) and covers the entire globe, including information such as the date, geolocation, and estimated number of casualties. Its aim is to provide the most comprehensive and systematically structured data on organized violence worldwide since 1989.

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Data Review:

The UCDP Georeferenced Event Dataset (GED) Version 25.1

The UCDP Georeferenced Event Dataset (GED) Version 25.1 is a spatially and temporally disaggregated dataset on fatal events from three types of organized violence (state-based conflict, non-state conflict, and one-sided violence) recorded by the Uppsala Conflict Data Program (UCDP) between 1 January 1989 and 31 December 2024. It features 385,918 fatal events from 61 state-based armed conflicts, including 11 wars, with each event coded across 49 variables. In the context of Eastern Europe, the South Caucasus, and Central Asia, it covers Ukraine, Russia, Azerbaijan, Tajikistan, Georgia, Kyrgyzstan, Armenia, Moldova, Uzbekistan, Romania, and Poland. The dataset aims to facilitate “conflict analyses below the state and country-year levels [providing] new insights into the geographical and temporal sequencing of warfare and violence.”¹

Methodological Foundation

The dataset’s unit of analysis is *event*, defined as “an incident where armed force was used by an organized actor against another organized actor, or against civilians, resulting in at least 1 direct death at a specific location and a specific date.”²

- *Armed force* is defined as the “use of arms in order to promote the parties’ general position in the conflict, resulting in deaths.”
- An *organized actor* is defined as “a government of an independent state, a formally organized group, or an informally organized group.”
- *Direct death* is defined as “a death relating to either combat between warring parties or violence against civilians.”
- *Specific location* is defined as “a name and one pair of latitude and longitude coordinates that relate to the geographical information specified in the source material.”
- *Specific date* is defined as “a specified time period during which armed interactions cause at least one fatality.”³

¹ Sundberg and Melander 2013, p. 526; Högbladh Stina, 2025, “UCDP GED Codebook version 25.1”, Department of Peace and Conflict Research, Uppsala University, p. 523

² Högbladh, Stina (2025). UCDP GED Codebook version 25.1. Department of Peace and Conflict Research, Uppsala University, p. 4.

³ Högbladh, Stina (2025). UCDP GED Codebook version 25.1. Department of Peace and Conflict Research, Uppsala University, p. 5

The dataset includes only events that occurred in the context of an armed conflict resulting in at least 25 battle-related deaths in one calendar year.⁴ To ensure accuracy, fatalities are reported as low, best, and high estimates.

Generally, three types of armed conflict are distinguished:

- *State-based*, defined as “a contested incompatibility concerning government and/or territory where [...] armed force [is used] between two parties, at least one of which is the government of a state.”
- *Non-state*, defined as “the use of armed force between two organized armed groups, neither of which is the government of a state.”
- *One-sided violence*, defined as “the deliberate use of armed force by the government of a state or by a formally organized group against civilians.”⁵

The events are recorded by UCDP monitors through a multi-stage, iterative process based on the monitoring and collection of open-source evidence. Media sources are selected from the Dow Jones Factiva aggregator for analysis in various languages, using a set of keywords (e.g., “kill,” “die,” “dead,” etc.). Additionally, local media, IO, INGO, and NGO reports, government publications, research papers, and other sources may be consulted on a case-by-case basis.

Coordinates in the WGS84 (EPSG SRID 4326) format, along with precision scores (indicating, for instance, whether the coordinates refer to a specific settlement or a larger administrative unit), are determined using Google Earth, Google Maps, Maplandia, Wikimapia, and other sources such as digital maps, NGO reports, and field atlases.⁶ Inconsistencies are resolved during regular meetings between coders and project managers. Each event can be associated with only one location, with village as the lowest level of spatial disaggregation.⁷ Airports are coded separately.

The time of each event is also recorded with a precision score, where one calendar day (from 00:00 to 23:59 local time) represents the lowest level of temporal disaggregation.⁸

After an event is included in the database, a project manager conducts additional consistency and streamlining checks to ensure data quality. Moreover, technical

⁴ Sundberg and Melander 2013, p. 526; Högladh Stina, 2025, “UCDP GED Codebook version 25.1”, Department of Peace and Conflict Research, Uppsala University, p. 525; UCDP (2024). UCDP Definitions - Uppsala University. [online] www.uu.se. Available at:

<https://www.uu.se/en/department/peace-and-conflict-research/research/ucdp/ucdp-definitions>.

⁵ UCDP (2024). UCDP Definitions - Uppsala University. [online] www.uu.se. Available at:

<https://www.uu.se/en/department/peace-and-conflict-research/research/ucdp/ucdp-definitions>.

⁶ Sundberg and Melander 2013, p. 526; Högladh Stina, 2025, “UCDP GED Codebook version 25.1”, Department of Peace and Conflict Research, Uppsala University, p. 526

⁷ Högladh, Stina (2025). UCDP GED Codebook version 25.1. Department of Peace and Conflict Research, Uppsala University, p. 20.

⁸ Högladh, Stina (2025). UCDP GED Codebook version 25.1. Department of Peace and Conflict Research, Uppsala University, p. 24.

consistency (e.g., correct coordinates, IDs, casualty numbers, etc.) is reinforced through over 50 automated tests, primarily using PHP and Python scripts.⁹

A full description of the methodological foundation of the UCDP GED can be found in the 2013 article by Ralph Sundberg and Erik Melander.¹⁰ For the specific methodology of GED 25.1, refer to the codebook by Stina Högladh.¹¹

Limitations

For reasons of theoretical validity, the dataset excludes instances of violence within armed conflicts that did not result in at least 25 battle-related deaths. It also considers only organized actors and primarily adopts a conservative approach to casualty estimation, including only deaths but not injuries. Unorganized forms of violence (e.g., riots, armed protests, murders, etc.) are not included in the dataset.

Usage

The dataset is primarily intended for quantitative analysis and can be partially integrated with several other UCDP datasets, as well as with the PRIO-GRID dataset at the spatial level.¹² It is available in CSV, Excel, R, and Stata formats and can be freely downloaded from the UCDP website.¹³ However, two citations are required:

- Davies, S., Pettersson, T., Sollenberg, M., & Öberg, M. (2025). Organized violence 1989–2024, and the challenges of identifying civilian victims. *Journal of Peace Research*, 62(4).
- Sundberg, Ralph and Erik Melander (2013) Introducing the UCDP Georeferenced Event Dataset. *Journal of Peace Research* 50(4).

The events are coded across 49 variables. The codebook used by the UCDP is provided below without modification.¹⁴

*Table 1. UCDP GED 25.1 Codebook.*¹⁵

Variable name	Content	Type
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⁹ Sundberg and Melander 2013, p. 526; Högladh Stina, 2025, “UCDP GED Codebook version 25.1”, Department of Peace and Conflict Research, Uppsala University, p. 15.

¹⁰ Sundberg and Melander 2013, p. 526; Högladh Stina, 2025, “UCDP GED Codebook version 25.1”, Department of Peace and Conflict Research, Uppsala University.

¹¹ Codebook 2025

¹² Sundberg, Ralph and Erik Melander (2013). Introducing the UCDP Georeferenced Event Dataset. *Journal of Peace Research* 50(4), p. 524

¹³ UCDP Dataset Download Center (2025). [online] Available at: https://ucdp.uu.se/downloads/index.html#ged_global.

¹⁴ Högladh, Stina (2025). UCDP GED Codebook version 25.1. Department of Peace and Conflict Research, Uppsala University, pp. 6-12.

¹⁵ Högladh, Stina (2025). UCDP GED Codebook version 25.1. Department of Peace and Conflict Research, Uppsala University.

id	A unique numeric ID identifying each event.	integer
relid	Only used in older versions of the dataset, exists but should not be used in the API 25.1 version, removed in other formats for UCDP GED 25.1	integer
year	The year of the event	integer
active_year	1: if the event belongs to an active conflict/dyad/actor-year 0: otherwise	integer
type_of_violence	Type of UCDP conflict: 1: state-based conflict 2: non-state conflict 3: one-sided violence	integer
code_status	Always clear, only used for monthly releases of candidate events, only available in the API 25.1 version, removed in the other formats for UCDP GED 25.1	integer
conflict_dset_id	Only used in older versions of the dataset, exists but should not be used in the API 25.1 version, removed in the other formats for UCDP GED 25.1.	integer
conflict_new_id	<p>A unique conflict identification code for each individual conflict in the dataset.</p> <p>UCDP Conflict ID for state based, non-state conflicts and one-sided violence as per the UCDP/PRIO Armed Conflict Dataset and UCDP Non-State Dataset and UCDP One-Sided dataset version 25.1.</p> <p>Fully compatible with UCDP/PRIO Armed Conflict Dataset, UCDP Non-State Dataset and UCDP OneSided Violence Dataset versions 17.1 and later.</p> <p>This identifier is unique across the dataset (i.e. a non-state conflict cannot have the same identifier as a state-based conflict or a one-sided instance), irrespective of type of violence, and may be used for filtering and aggregation.</p> <p>Warning: Not compatible with pre-17.1 versions of any UCDP datasets.</p>	integer

conflict_name	Name of the UCDP conflict to which the event belongs. For non-state conflicts and one-sided violence this is the same as the dyad name.	string(9999)
dyad_dset_id	Only used in older versions of the dataset, exists but should not be used in the API 25.1 version, removed in the other formats for UCDP GED 25.1.	integer
dyad_new_id	<p>A unique conflict identification code for each individual dyad in the dataset.</p> <p>UCDP Dyad ID for state based conflicts, non-state conflicts and one-sided incidences as per the UCDP/PRIO Armed Conflict Dataset, UCDP NonState Dataset and UCDP One-Sided Violence Datasets versions 25.1.</p> <p>Fully compatible with UCDP/PRIO Armed Conflict Dataset, UCDP Non-State Dataset and UCDP OneSided Violence Dataset versions 17.1 and later.</p> <p>This identifier is unique across the dataset (i.e. a non-state conflict cannot have the same identifier as a state-based conflict or a one-sided instance), irrespective of type of violence, and may be used for filtering and aggregation.</p> <p>Warning: Not compatible with pre-17.1 versions of any UCDP datasets.</p>	integer
dyad_name	<p>Name of the conflict dyad creating the event.</p> <p>A dyad is the pair of two actors engaged in violence (in the case of one-sided violence, the perpetrator of violence and civilians).</p> <p>The two sides are separated by an ASCII dash (e.g. Government of Russia — Caucasus Emirate, Taliban — civilians).</p>	string(9999)
side_a_dset_id	Only used in older versions of the dataset, exists but should not be used in the API 25.1 version, removed in the other formats for UCDP GED 25.1.	integer
side_a_new_id	A unique ID of side A.	integer

	<p>Fully compatible with UCDP/PRIO Armed Conflict Dataset, UCDP Non-State Dataset and UCDP OneSided Violence Dataset versions 17.1 and later.</p> <p>Warning: Not compatible with pre-17.1 versions of any UCDP datasets.</p> <p>Note that this ID is no longer the Gleditsch and Ward number for State actors/sides. If you need that identifier, use gwnoa described below</p>	
side_a	The name of Side A in the dyad. In state-based conflicts always a government. In one-sided violence always the perpetrating party.	string(9999)
side_b_dset_id	Only used in older versions of the dataset, exists but should not be used in the API 25.1 version, removed in the other formats for UCDP GED 25.1.	integer
side_b_new_id	<p>A unique ID of side B.</p> <p>Fully compatible with UCDP/PRIO Armed Conflict Dataset, UCDP Non-State Dataset and UCDP OneSided Violence Dataset versions 17.1 and later.</p> <p>Warning: Not compatible with pre-17.1 versions of any UCDP datasets.</p> <p>Note that this ID is no longer the Gleditsch and Ward number for State actors/sides. If you need that identifier, use gwnob described below</p>	integer
side_b	The name of Side B in the dyad. In state-based conflicts always a government. In one-sided violence always the perpetrating party.	string(9999)
number_of_sources	<p>Number of total sources containing information for an event that were consulted.</p> <p>Note that this variable is only available for data collected since 2013 and for recently revised events. For older data, -1. Note that -1 does not mean information on the source is missing; reference to the source material is always available in the source_article field</p>	integer

source_article	<p>References to the names, dates and titles of the source material from which information on the event is gathered.</p> <p>A reference to at least one source material is available for ALL EVENTS.</p> <p>This variable is highly streamlined for information collected since 2013, and is less so for older data. For such older data, abbreviations are sometimes used for source agencies</p>	text
source_office	<p>The name of the organizations publishing the source materials.</p> <p>Note that this variable is only available for data collected since 2013, and for recently revised events. For older data, the field is empty. Note that an empty field does not mean information on the source is missing; reference to the source text 9/52 material is always available in the source_article field, for every event.</p>	text
source_date	<p>The dates the source materials were published on.</p> <p>Note that this variable is only available for data collected since 2013, and for recently revised events. For older data, the field is empty. Note that an empty field does not mean information on the source is missing; reference to the source material is always available in the source_article field, for every event.</p> <p>1753-01-01 is set as a default date when the date is missing.</p>	text
source_headline	<p>The titles of the source materials.</p> <p>Note that this variable is available for all data collected after 2014, for most data collected in 2013 and for recently revised events. For older data, the field is empty. Note that an empty field does not mean information on the source is missing; reference to the source material is always available in the source_article field, for every event.</p>	text
source_original	The name or type of person or organization	string(9999)

	<p>from which the information about the event originates in the original report.</p> <p>e.g. "police", "Lt. Col. Johnson", "eyewitnesses", "rebel spokesman".</p>	
where_prec	<p>The precision with which the coordinates and location assigned to the event reflects the location of the actual event.</p> <p>1: exact location of the event known and coded. 2: event occurred within at maximum a ca. 25 km radius around a known point. The coded point is the known point. 3: only the second order administrative division where an event happened is known. That administrative division is coded with a point representing it (typically the centroid). 4: only the first order administrative division where an event happened is known. That administrative division is coded with a point representing it (typically the centroid). 5: the only spatial reference for the event is neither a known point nor a known formal administrative division, but rather a linear feature (e.g. a long river, a border, a longer road or the line connecting two locations further afield than 25 km) or a fuzzy polygon without defined borders (informal regions, large radiuses etc.). A representation point is chosen for the feature and employed. 6: only the country where the event took place in is known. 7: event in international waters or airspace.</p>	integer
where_coordinates	Name of the location to which the event is assigned. Fully standardized and normalized.	string(9999)
where_description	Comment on the location coded, sometimes left empty. Can include the area of the capital or name of a village that has not been found.	string
adm_1	Name of the first order (largest) administrative division where the event took place	string(9999)
adm_2	Name of the second order administrative division where the event took place	string(9999)
latitude	Latitude (in decimal degrees)	numeric(9,6)

longitude	Longitude (in decimal degrees)	numeric(9,6)
geom_wkt	An Open Geospatial Consortium textual representation of the location of each individual point. Formatted as OGC WKT (<i>well known text</i>) without SRID.	string(9999)
priogrid_gid	<p>The PRIO-GRID cell id (gid) in which the event took place. Compatibility with PRIO-GRID (Tollefsen, 2012) is guaranteed for both PRIO-GRID 1 and 2.</p> <p>Warning: We associate every point to the PRIOGRID that contains it, even if the point is in another country than the one officially assigned to the respective PRIO-GRID cell through their majority area rule. It is your responsibility to make sure the covariates for the PRIO-GRID cell are correct for each event. Further, for the same reason, DO NOT, under any circumstances, first clip out (subset) PRIO-GRID by country before merging with UCDP GED as data loss will certainly occur. Refer to your copy of the PRIO-GRID for further details on PRIOGRID's majority assignment rule (p.3 in PRIOGRID's original codebook).</p>	integer
country	Name of the country in which the event takes place	string(999)
country_id	Gleditsch and Ward number of the country in which the event takes place.	integer
region	Region where the event took place. One of following: {Africa, Americas, Asia, Europe, Middle East}	string(999)
event_clarity	<p>1 (high) for events where the reporting allows the coder to identify the event in full. That is, events where the individual happening is described by the original source in a sufficiently detailed way as to identify individual incidents, i.e. separate activities of fighting in a single location:</p> <p>Example of such reporting: <i>“2 people were killed in Banda Aceh town on the 9th of December in fighting between the government and GAM when a car exploded in a main market.”</i></p>	integer

	<p>2 (lower) for events where an aggregation of information was already made by the source material that is impossible to undo in the coding process. Such events are described by the original source only as aggregates (totals) of multiple separate activities of fighting spanning over a longer period than a single, clearly defined day.</p> <p>Examples of such reporting: <i>“The Ukrainian government informs that 29 people have died in the past six days in a number of clashes with the separatists along the line of conflict.”</i></p>	
date_prec	<p>How precise the information is about the date of an event.</p> <p>1: exact date of event is known; 2: the date of the event is known only within a 2-6 day range. 3: only the week of the event is known 4: the date of the event is known only within an 8- 30 day range or only the month when the event has taken place is known 5: the date of the event is known only within a range longer than one month but not more than one calendar year.</p>	integer
date_start	The earliest possible date when the event has taken place.	Date YYYY-MM-DD
date_end	The last possible date when the event has taken place.	Date YYYY-MM-DD
deaths_a	<p>The best estimate of deaths sustained by side a.</p> <p>Always 0 for one-sided violence events.</p>	integer
deaths_b	<p>The best estimate of deaths sustained by side b.</p> <p>Always 0 for one-sided violence events.</p>	integer
deaths_civilians	<p>The best estimate of dead civilians in the event.</p> <p>For non-state or state-based events, this is the number of collateral damage resulting in</p>	integer

	fighting between side a and side b. For one-sided violence, it is the number of civilians killed by side a.	
deaths_unknown	The best estimate of deaths of persons of unknown status.	integer
best	The best (most likely) estimate of total fatalities resulting from an event. It is always the sum of deaths_a, deaths_b, deaths_civilians and deaths_unknown	integer
high	The highest reliable estimate of total fatalities.	integer
low	The lowest reliable estimate of total fatalities.	integer
gwnoa	The Gleditsch and Ward number for Side A if the side is a state. Empty if Side A is not a state.	string(9999)
gwnob	The Gleditsch and Ward number for Side B if the side is a state. Empty if Side B is not a state.	string(9999)
geom / geometry	An Open Geospatial Consortium / ESRI binary representation of each individual point. Contains the SRID (4326) where supported. Due to the binary nature of this variable, this variable is contained only in the formats that support it.	geometry (Point, 4326)

Regarding the country-specific data, GED 25.1 provides data on:

- 31,547 events involving Ukraine;
- 4,616 events involving Russia (Soviet Union);
- 800 events involving Azerbaijan;
- 328 events involving Tajikistan;
- 259 events involving Georgia;
- 83 events involving Kyrgyzstan;
- 77 events involving Armenia;
- 77 events involving Moldova;
- 32 events involving Uzbekistan;
- 16 events involving Romania;
- 1 event involving Poland.

In terms of specific conflicts, the dataset features:

- 28,499 events on Russia and Ukraine;
- 2,633 events on Ukraine and Novorossiia (by “Novorossiia,” UCDP refers to the armed forces of the so-called Luhansk People’s Republic (LPR) and Donetsk People’s Republic (DPR));¹⁶
- 1,807 events on Russia (Soviet Union) and Chechnya;
- 1,476 events on Russia (Soviet Union) and the Caucasus Emirate;
- 863 events on Azerbaijan and Artsakh (Nagorno-Karabakh);
- 667 events on Ukraine and Donetsk (by “Donetsk,” UCDP refers to the so-called Donetsk People’s Republic (DPR));¹⁷
- 404 events on the Government of Russia (Soviet Union) and Civilians;
- 294 events on Ukraine and Luhansk (by “Luhansk,” UCDP refers to the so-called Luhansk People’s Republic (LPR));¹⁸
- 273 events on Tajikistan and the Government (by this, UCDP mainly refers to confrontations between the United Tajik Opposition (UTO), the People’s Front of Tajikistan (PFT), the Islamic Movement of Uzbekistan (IMU), and the government);¹⁹
- 144 events on Georgia and Abkhazia;
- 132 events on Russia and the Islamic State;
- 77 events on Moldova and Dniestr (by “Dniestr,” UCDP refers to the so-called Pridnestrovian Moldavian Republic (PMR));²⁰
- 67 events on Russia (Soviet Union) and the Government (by this, UCDP refers to incursions of the Freedom of Russia Legion (LSR) and Russian Volunteer Corps (RDK) into Russia during 2023–2024);²¹
- 65 events on Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan;
- 57 events on Uzbekistan and the Government (by this, UCDP mainly refers to clashes between the government of Islam Karimov and the Islamic Movement of Uzbekistan (IMU) in 1999–2000, and the Jihad Islamic Group (JIG) in 2004);²²
- 48 events on the Chechen Republic of Ichkeria and Civilians;

¹⁶ UCDP. (2024b). UCDP - Uppsala Conflict Data Program. [online] Available at: <https://ucdp.uu.se/conflict/13306>.

¹⁷ UCDP. (2025). UCDP - Uppsala Conflict Data Program. [online] Available at: <https://ucdp.uu.se/conflict/13246>.

¹⁸ UCDP. (2025b). UCDP - Uppsala Conflict Data Program. [online] Available at: <https://ucdp.uu.se/conflict/13247>.

¹⁹ UCDP. (2025c). UCDP - Uppsala Conflict Data Program. [online] Available at: <https://ucdp.uu.se/conflict/395>.

²⁰ UCDP. (2025d). UCDP - Uppsala Conflict Data Program. [online] Available at: <https://ucdp.uu.se/conflict/394>.

²¹ UCDP. (2025e). UCDP - Uppsala Conflict Data Program. [online] Available at: <https://ucdp.uu.se/conflict/399>.

²² UCDP. (2025f). UCDP - Uppsala Conflict Data Program. [online] Available at: <https://ucdp.uu.se/conflict/415>.

- 48 events on Georgia and the Government (by this, UCDP refers to clashes between the Zviadists—pro-Gamsakhurdia forces—and the new Georgian government in 1991–1993);²³
- 48 events on Georgia and South Ossetia;
- 40 events on Russia (Soviet Union) and Nagorno-Karabakh;
- 38 events on the Forces of the Caucasus Emirate and Civilians;
- 18 events on the Republic of Georgia and the Republic of South Ossetia;
- 14 events on the Government of Tajikistan and Civilians;
- 11 events on Azerbaijan and the Government (by this, UCDP refers to clashes between a military faction led by Suret Huseynov and President Elchibey in 1993, and the mutiny by the special police forces OPON against President Heydar Aliyev in 1995);²⁴
- 10 events on Romania and the Government (by this, UCDP refers to violent mass protests against President Ceausescu in 1989);²⁵
- 9 events on Armenians and Azeris (by this, UCDP refers to interethnic conflict between Armenians and Azeris in the Soviet Union);²⁶
- 8 events on the Republic of Abkhazia and Civilians;
- 7 events on Russia (Soviet Union) and Azerbaijan;
- 6 events on the Chechen Republic of Ichkeria and the Provisional Council of the Chechen Republic;
- 6 events on the Government of Romania and Civilians (by this, UCDP refers to one-sided violence against civilians in 1989);²⁷
- 6 events on Ukraine and the Government (by this, UCDP refers to violence during the Maidan protests in 2014);²⁸
- 5 events on the Republic of Abkhazia and the White Legion;
- 4 events on Russia (Soviet Union) and Dagestan;
- 4 events on Tajikistan and the Islamic State;
- 3 events on the Forest Brothers, the White Legion, and the Republic of Abkhazia;
- 2 events on the Republic of Artsakh and Civilians;
- 1 event on the Chechen Republic of Ichkeria and the Forces of Ruslan Labazanov;

²³ UCDP. (2025g). UCDP - Uppsala Conflict Data Program. [online] Available at: <https://ucdp.uu.se/conflict/380>.

²⁴ UCDP. (2025h). UCDP - Uppsala Conflict Data Program. [online] Available at: <https://ucdp.uu.se/conflict/396>.

²⁵ UCDP. (2025i). UCDP - Uppsala Conflict Data Program. [online] Available at: <https://ucdp.uu.se/conflict/370>.

²⁶ UCDP. (2025j). UCDP - Uppsala Conflict Data Program. [online] Available at: <https://ucdp.uu.se/nonstate/5419>.

²⁷ UCDP. (2025k). UCDP - Uppsala Conflict Data Program. [online] Available at: <https://ucdp.uu.se/onesided/919>.

²⁸ UCDP. (2025l). UCDP - Uppsala Conflict Data Program. [online] Available at: <https://ucdp.uu.se/conflict/13219>.

- 1 event on Supporters of independence for Eastern Ukraine and Supporters of Ukrainian unity (by this, UCDP refers to violent clashes in Odesa in 2014).²⁹

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Note

This data review was produced by Anhelina Hrytsei as part of an Erasmus Traineeship at the Research Center for East European Studies at the University of Bremen.

²⁹ UCDP. (2025m). UCDP - Uppsala Conflict Data Program. [online] Available at: <https://ucdp.uu.se/nonstate/14113>.